

A STUDY OF B.ED. COURSE TRAINEE TEACHERS ATTITUDES TOWARDS USE OF ICT IN THE TRAINING

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Introduction:

Role of the teacher utilizing ICT Teachers remain central to the learning process. A shift in the role of a teacher utilizing ICTs to that of a facilitator does not remove the need for teachers to serve as leaders in the classroom; traditional teacher leadership skills and practices are still important (especially those related to lesson planning, preparation, and follow-up). Teacher lesson planning is vital when using ICTs; where little planning has occurred; research shows that student work is often unfocused and can result in lower attainment.

Pedagogy- Introducing technology alone will not change the teaching and learning process but ICTs can enable teachers to transform their teacher practices, given a set of enabling conditions. Teachers' pedagogical practices and reasoning influence their uses of ICT, and the nature of teacher ICT use impacts student achievement.

ICTs seen as tools to help teachers create more 'learner-centric' learning environments:-The most effective uses of ICT are those in which the teacher, aided by ICTs, can challenge pupils' understanding and thinking, either through whole-class discussions and individual/small group work using ICTs. ICTs are seen as important tools to enable and support the move from traditional '**teacher-centric**' teaching styles to more '**learner-centric**' methods.

ICTs can be used to support change and to support/extend existing teaching practices: Pedagogical practices of teachers using ICT can range from only small enhancements of teaching practices using what are essentially traditional methods, to more fundamental changes in their approach to teaching. ICTs can be used to reinforce existing pedagogical practices as well as to change the way teachers and students interact.

Using ICTs as tools for information presentation is of mixed effectiveness:-The use of ICTs as presentation tools (through overhead and LCD projectors, television, electronic whiteboards, guided "web-tours", where students simultaneously view the same resources on computer screens) is seen to be of diverse effectiveness. While it may promote class understanding of and discussion about difficult concepts (especially through the display of simulations), such uses of ICTs can re-enforce traditional pedagogical practices and divert focus from the content of what is being discussed or displayed to the tool being utilized.

Technological Competencies along with teaching learning principles.

Teacher technical abilities and knowledge of ICTs: The demands of the 21st century information rich and knowledge based society make it essential for both teachers and students to utilize technology effectively. The point has been made that within a sound educational setting; technology can empower and enable students to be capable information technology users, information seekers, analyzers, evaluators, problem solvers & decision maker.

ICT and teachers attitude an effective educational environment is also characterized by a positive school climate where the teachers and students feel good about teaching and learning and cooperate to foster a caring attitude. Attitude has great importance in learning and teaching. It is one of the important objectives of teaching and learning to develop attitudes in the aspects and process of school subjects. A review of research studies reveals that teacher effectiveness is related to attitude towards ICT and technology competence of teachers. So Researchers felt that the successful utilization of technologies in the classroom depends mainly on the teachers 'attitudes toward ICT tools. Attitudes are key factors in whether teachers accept computer as a teaching tool in their teaching practices. Keeping all these views in the mind researcher the researcher has undertaken this study to find out the teachers attitude towards ICT.

Statement of the Problem:

“A Study of B.Ed. Course Trainee Teachers Attitudes towards Use ICT in the training”

❖ **Objectives of the Study:** The study has been planned with the following objectives-

- To study the attitude of teachers towards ICT use.
 - To declare the level of technology competence among teachers.
- ❖ **Hypotheses of the Study:** There is a significant positive relationship between the extents of ICT use by teachers and their attitude towards ICT.
- ❖ **Methodology:** In this study, a quantitative method of data collection was used to collect and analyses the data obtained from the respondents. The investigator used ICT Attitude Scale for pre service Teachers
- ❖ **Sample:** The study engaged 200 pre service teachers from five different B.Ed. colleges who were selected through randomization technique in order to avoid any kind of prejudices
- ❖ **Tool:** In order to collect data, researcher provided ICT Attitude Scale for pre service Teachers having 34 statements that helped to analyses the existing skills among pre service teachers.
- ❖ **Analysis and Interpretation:** Descriptive and inferential statistics both were used to analyze the data. The below given table shows there is a significant positive relationship between the extents of ICT us To study the attitude of teachers towards **ICT**, scores of the respondents on the ‘ICT Attitude Scale’ were arranged in ascending order. After classifying the independent variable attitude toward ICT as negative, neutral and positive; the number of the respondents lining in each classification were calculated and converted into percentages as shown in table.

TABLE

Variable Description	Score	N	Percentage%
Negative Attitude towards ICT	≤ 117	28	14
Neutral Attitude towards ICT	In between 117 & 147	144	72
Positive Attitude towards ICT	≥ 147	28	14
Total		200	100

Interpretation:

Table - shows score ranges of the independent variable ‘Attitude towards **ICT**’ of research as less than equal to score 117, greater than equal to score 147 and score in between 117 & 147 for negative, positive and neutral attitude towards **ICT** respectively. Equal number of respondents lies in the sample with negative and positive attitude towards **ICT** i.e. 28 in each category, which is the 14 percent of the whole sample of teachers. Nearly three fourth of respondents from total sample of 200 teachers have neutral attitude towards **ICT** i.e. 144 respondents, which is 72 percent of the total sample of teachers. This

clearly shows that secondary school teachers differ in their attitude towards ICT.

Conclusion:

The use of technology in everyday teaching and learning activities appears to be more important than specific instruction in "computer classes". While the development of technology skills is seen to have a role in the teaching and learning process, it is more important as an enabler of other teaching and learning practices, and not too important in and of itself. Schools that report the highest levels of student ICT-related skills and experience are often not those with heavy computer course requirements, but rather ones that made use of ICTs on a routine basis throughout the teacher professional development and the teaching and learning process.

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